

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B261
Date: 22 January 2007
Take Off 09:54:40
Landing: 14:11:58
Flight Time 4h17m18

Campaign: WINTEX – Snow Drift / Satellite overpass

Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	AVAPS / CCM2 / Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Nina Petersen	UEA
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	MARSS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
11	SWS Training	Jeff Brown	Met Office
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Flight Track:

B261 Track 23-JAN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B261
 Date: 23/01/2007
 Project: WINTEX
 Location: N Sea and East Anglia

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095440		T/O			Cranfield
100743		event	11.0 kft	057	JW Nev zero
100933		event	11.0 kft	052	Heimann reset
100948		event	11.0 kft	043	BBR retract
101137	102317	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.21 kft	034	QNH 1018
102518	102559	Profile 1	-.04 - 0.05 kft	284	
102608	103108	Run 1.1	0.10 kft	284	
103335	103642	Profile 2	0.12 - 2.9 kft	114	
104036	110929	Run 2.1	2.9 kft	252	
104508		event	3.0 kft	272	Nevzorov reset
104547		event	2.9 kft	274	Nevzorov zero
105143		event	2.9 kft	099	Nevzorov reset
105203		event	2.9 kft	090	Nevzorov zero
110940	111116	Profile 3	3.0 - 4.4 kft	214	
111346	114332	Run 3.1	4.4 kft	069	
111346		event			JW Nevzorov zero
113000		event			P0 frozen?
114216		event	4.4 kft	003	change tapes
114430		event	4.4 kft	308	end run
114500		event	3.5 kft	257	descend to unfreeze P0
115056	115449	Run 4.1	0.06 - 0.01 kft	102	
115506	115933	Run 4.2	0.1 kft	104	
120604	121655	Profile 4	0.05 - 11.0 kft	312	
122910	123927	Profile 5	7.0 - 0.08 kft	338	
123936	125119	Run 5.1	0.07 - 0.13 kft	125	
125119	125812	Profile 6	0.13 - 8.5 kft	312	
130001	130532	Run 6.1	8.5 kft	090	
131508	132753	Run 7.1	8.1 - 8.0 kft	333	
132753	133307	Profile 7	8.5 - 13.0 kft	071	
133807	135936	Run 8.1	13.0 - 7.3 kft	316	
134052		event	13.0 kft	312	launch sonde 1
141158		Land	0.17 kft	255	Cranfield
141801		event	0.16 kft	309	final position 52 04.36N 0 37.48W

B261 Track 23-JAN-07

WINTEX Sortie Brief – Decay of Snow Showers over East Anglia

Date : 23rd January 2006

Flight Number : B261

Mission Scientist : Clare Lee and Jonathan Taylor.

Sortie Aims: The Met Office Unified Model shows consistent problems (in common with all other forecast models) with representing precipitation drift. Convection is triggered over the warm grid boxes of the North Sea and the precipitation is assumed to fall into the same grid box. In reality as the cells move over land the precipitation will drift with the wind and can fall significant distances inland (up to 100km). In addition, if the cells are of sufficient size then despite the land temperatures not being sufficient to act as a source of convection it may take some finite time for them to die out and hence the inward penetration of the precipitation will be greater. This sortie aims to map the development of the snow and convection between the North Sea and over East Anglia.

Sortie Location: Southern N.Sea and N.Norfolk preferred with NE or Easterly winds.

Communications / special info:

Weather conditions: Open cell convection over North Sea being advected over land.

Instrument requirements:

- JW / Nevzorov to be zeroed when in clear air at any altitude when straight / level.
- Cloud physics console. Normal operation of all probes
- CDP - operating
- Turbulence probe – monitor performance when in icing conditions.

Sortie detail:

- (a) T+0 Take-off Cranfield, transit to operating area over the sea descending to 50ft just off Norfolk Coast, after take off we must climb to greater than 5000ft to allow mission scientist laptop to be deployed. (15 min)
- (b) T+15 Straight and level run at 100ft to position off Norfolk coast approx: 52deg55minN, 1deg 30min E (10 min).
- (c) T+25 Profile to level where temperature = -3deg C and fly random walk run through convective cells at this altitude (15 min)
- (d) T+40 Continue random walk through cells at same temperature layer in legs roughly oriented perpendicular to wind starting close to coast and moving inland penetrating several cells at distances roughly every 10km inland (60min)
- (e) T+100 Repeat item (d) at temp = -8deg C level working from inland position back towards coast (60min)
- (f) T+160 Stepped profile to level of average cloud top (20min)
- (g) T+180 Repeat item (d) (60)
- (h) T+240 Repeat item (e) as time permits.
- (i) T+295 Recover to Cranfield
- (j) T+315 Land

Mission scientist Debrief

B261 23/01/07

Snow drift sortie around East Anglia

Mission scientist – Clare Lee

Summary

This sortie was to investigate the evolution of Cu clouds and the associated snow drift as it came from the sea to over the land. A number of Cu cells were measured at three different altitudes. Problems were encountered with a frozen turbulence probe which shortened the science.

Weather

Isolated Cu cells (from 3 to 11kft), the largest of which had active cores producing snow which did reach the ground. Clear sky was observed between the cells. Initially the more active cells were over land. The cells aligned themselves with the coast as they came inland. Towards the end of the sorties the ones over the sea were much more active, which had previously been very shallow.

Sortie

A profile descent from FL110 to 50ft was made in the operating area. The Cu clouds consisted of large snow and ice. A run at 100ft was made, followed by a profile climb to 3000ft (approximately -4 C). A run at 3000ft was made in a random walk manner to penetrate a large sample of cells. Mainly wet snow was observed, with some needles and columns in the boundary edges. The random walk was then repeated at 4500ft (approx -8 C), after a profile ascent. As time evolved some of the Cu became less active. At 1138 the pitot static probe became iced, hence a profile descent was made to defrost the probe. After 15 mins at 250ft the probe appeared to be functioning normally and a profile ascent was made to FL110. At this point the probe froze again, so another descent was made to 100ft. After defrosting at 100ft a profile ascent was made to 8500ft (average cloud top height), where a random walk through the Cu tops was made. More freezing of the turbulence probes was encountered, so the science was ended with a profile to FL130 over the sea and a drop sonde was launched such that it would penetrate one of the deep Cu cells. Transit back to Cranfield

Instrument Status

Cloud physics – PCASP very noisy and hence switched off part way through. 2DP have some problems towards the end

MARSS – OK, except ch16 and laptop not communicating with the inst correctly.

SWS – OK. Training exercise only

AVAPS – OK

Chem – OK

Core – icing problems on turbulence probes. Nev failed after first heavy ice.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

CUARE LEE

Flight No **B.B.261...**

Date **23/1/07.....**

Page **1** of **5**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:07:43					T10 Cranfield
					Convective clouds over
					Muske. bases ~ 3kft. tops ~
					1kft.
101137	P1	FZ 110			Profile descent.
					It's going through cloud seeing
					snow. Heading for active part on radar.
		7000ft			Large snow + ice
					T = -3 Alt = ~ 2.5kft.
					T = -8 Alt = ~ 4.5kft.
102317	Pint.				Intercepting due to air traffic
					Small W puffs (~4kft) over sea.
102518	P1ec.		289		No precip at or belows.
					Land is enhancing convection.
102500	P1ec	500ft.			Sea choppy v. few white caps though.
102608	R1.1	100ft.	284	52° 34' N 1024' E	wind 13ms ⁻¹ / 20°
103108	R1.lead	100ft.			Run end. + turn to right.
103335	P2	100ft.			Profile climb.
					Can see cells precipitating over land
103642	P2end	3000ft.			none over sea.
		3000ft.			T = -4.38 T _D = -6.6°C.
103942.					below cloud base over sea. lower over
					land. Heading for active cell.
104036	R2.1	3000ft.			Transitioning from sea over land.
104134		3000ft.	249.		Entering cloud. 2DC wet snow
					small ice - low concn.
					then water large droplets.
					+ small ice.
					T = -5.6°C. T _D = -2.85°C.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.261** Date **23/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104329			276		Turning for next active cell on radar. Going through edges of non active
104620			271		In cloud. heading for centre of cell. → they are precipitating.
1047					Wet snow on 2DC. - can be v. large flakes up to 5mm
104825			174		Turning left for next active area. boundary edge ⇒ needles.
					T = -4, T _D = -8.8°C in clear sky.
					Clouds broken, convective cells distant from each other.
105819					Start cloud. wet snow large size range. T = -4.76 T _D = -4.6°C. water edge at coast.
110029		3000ft.			large snow + columns, very few water drops
110405			328		cloud at coast bases @ 3000ft touching base no cloud phys. seen.
					T = -4.0, T _D = -5.3
110654		3000ft.	224	52°30'N 1°24'E	In cloud wet snow + occasional columns
110940	R2.1st.	3000ft.			Out of cloud
110940	P3	3000ft.	214		Profile climb.
111116	P3.2nd.	4500ft.			End climb turning to go through previous clouds at higher level. clear sky → T = -7.2, T _D = -10.4°C. Wind 11ms ⁻¹ /116°
111346	R3.1st.	4500ft.			
111607		4500ft.	261	52°24'N 1°36'E	Entering cloud. bursts of large wet snow. + some columns. T = -8.8, T _D = -5.87

111803 4500ft.

Out of cloud.

Boundary of clouds is very structured \Rightarrow patches of ice/snow. Some \hookrightarrow not as active or high as others. \Rightarrow less than 4.5kft. tops. Larger \hookrightarrow seem to be not as active as were 10 mins ago.

112241 262

In large \hookrightarrow cloud (precipitating at bottom). Temp $-7.3^{\circ}\text{C} \rightarrow -7.9^{\circ}\text{C}$

$T_D = -5.4 \rightarrow -8.3^{\circ}\text{C}$

Wet snow + smaller fragmentation (small ice).
 \hookrightarrow large

112510 4500ft.

Out of cloud.

Clear sky $T = -7.46^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -8.99$

112837 4500ft. 232
280

In cloud. Snow + drops (supercooled water).

112946

All droplets $T = -7.3$, $T_D = -8.15^{\circ}\text{C}$

Having to manoeuvre within cloud due to air traffic.

Snow observed on ground.

Coast cloud forming line \perp to wind direction.

113540

In cloud (which is precipitating) has a very small but very active core on radar.

$T = -8$, $T_D \approx -8$

113842

Edges \Rightarrow columns

at cloud. Probes (1.1kft) starting to show signs of icing.

113950

In cloud. + quickly ~~at~~ at then in again. Need to wait for air traffic before descend.

11 R. 4500ft. 2250ft.

Now more active convection over sea. ~~over~~ End Run. Descending to deice tub-probe.

$T = -3^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Much more active over sea now - deeper \hookrightarrow + see precip.

1156 RL 250ft.

Running at 250 to wait for probe to deice.
 $T \approx -3^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_D = -2.1$

B261

23/1107

CLARE LEE

415

1200

120550

120604

R4 ↑ 250ft.

2500ft.

120837

7800ft.

120947

4200ft.

121004

4420ft.

121200

6500ft.

121655

R6 end

FL110.

123203

P5 ↓

123927

P5 end

123936

R5.1 100ft.

1250

R5.1 end 100ft.

125119

R6 ↑ 100ft.

125812

R6 end 8500ft.

130001

R6-1 8500ft.

130337

130532

R6.1 end 8500ft.

descending to 100ft to try and get probe deiced.

$T = 3.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_D = -1.31^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Turning around probe slowly coming back. (Pitot-static).

Probe seems to be back.

Profiling up to cloud top alt.

clear sky. Heading towards a convective core in the profile.

$T = -2.93^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_D = -5.18^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In cloud. Snow + columns

Out other side. Heading towards next core.

In cloud. edge snowlike

Out other side. more ice aggregates as going up.

Cloud tops are now lower than previously

Turbulence probe iced again.

Descending to deice.

Run oversea to try + deice probe.

Turbulence probe recovered.

Profile + End run

Profile End. at cloud top height.

$T = -16.41$, $T_D = -25.96^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Running through cloud tops.

Seeing snowflakes as touching tops.

In cloud top. \Rightarrow snow. oversea.

$T = -16.74$, $T_D = -16.7$

End run - heading over land to area measured earlier.

718 \rightarrow 818 ω over ocean not deep enough convection though. Now a gap of cloud between coast + original clouds

B261

23/1/07

CLARE LEE

315

8000ft. 261

we were measuring. Transitioning over to original clouds. Forming a line across the country. I to wind. In cloud. - snow.

$T = -16.3$, $T_D = -13.44^\circ C$.

131508 R7.1

8000ft. 317

131905

Out of cloud. Can see aircraft wake (in RTC.) formed in the top of the cloud.

132110.

In ^{at} cloud. Sideslip probe iced up?

132228

In cloud. snow of all sizes. } The cores which are just coming in land.

132338

In cloud. Definitely lost sideslip probe.

132657

In cloud. Profile climb to be able to drop sonde. (RD93) old type. wind $12ms^{-1}/19^\circ$ clear sky profile.

132822 P7↑ 8500ft.

FZ110

133307 P7end FZ130

117

Profile end. turning right towards cloud, so can drop sonde through. Pitot-static probe icing?

133807 R8.1 FZ130

Wind $13ms^{-1}/15^\circ$; $T = -21.4^\circ$; $T_D = -38.7^\circ$

134052 S1 FZ130 313

Drop sonde through cloud. data all OK. - see increase T_D showing cloud.

134623 Sonde flash down.

End science transit back to Cranfield.

Last status
FSSP - ran without probs.
SIDI² + 2DC - all OK.
PCASP switched off - noisy
port way through 2DP probs. towards end - lots single pixd images
MASS - all except ch16
Laptop not communicating properly.
SWS - OK. Training only.
AVAPS - OK.
Chem - OK.
Core - icing of probes, New. failed after 1st heavy ice.
DFC - visiting scientist position - extremely dark.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B261

Date: 23 Jan 07	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
095000																SID1 recording (E) drive SID2 recording FFSSP recording CIP recording 2DP 2DC PCASP recording	
095500																Heaters on after T/O	
				1000	1000	<500									2	Profile 1	
102600	25	0.11	75	10	10	0	0	0	0							Run 1 100ft	
103108																End run 1	
104040																Run2.1 start	
104240																In cloud	
104800															2	In cloud	
105100	>1000		422	2000	2000	500	500	>1000	5000						2		
															6	Columns an exit from cloud edge	
																Sid2 screen very slow to appear	
105820			437	1000											2	Entering cloud	
110120																Wet snow, columns towards edge of cloud	
110700																Wet snow	
110900			558	1000		300	800									End run	
111346																Start run 3.1	
111708						500	500									Wet snow, columns	
112239																Enter cloud	
112500			804	2000		400	800									Wet snow	
112829																Enter cloud	
																Snow and drops	
113054			900	1000		200	800									Wet snow	
113555																Entering cloud	
																Columns	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B261 **T/O:** 09:54:40
Date of flight: 23/01/07 **Land:** 14:11:58

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B261
Date of Flight: 23/01/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	44537 blocks
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 247896
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 47978 Blocks written = 47978 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 095000 End = 141500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA?Y Are they non-zero in size?Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Some noise on 2DP after 132000 Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 095000 End = 141500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 095000 End = 141500</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 9744, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B261
Date of Flight: 23/01/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	Y
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 095000 141500
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK? Y

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 261** Date **23/1/07** Operat or(s) **Jeff Braon . Andy Wilson** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

083000	-	0	120°	VAR	NOT FITTED	- ALL OTHER OK ON STARTUP			
095800			6° F			Head to Zenith			
095908			6° F	250		Trist time to 250ms		✓	
100100			6° F			No flat line on dark setting		✓	
100200		11000	6° F			Shutters re-set - flat line achieved	✓	✓	✓
100315		11000	6° F	750			✓		
100330		11000	6° F	300		1/8 Secs Thin Ci above.		✓	✓
100345		11000	6° F	1000		Light dusting snow/frost.			✓
100359		11000	6°						
101137	P1	11000				Profile descent			
101221			6° F	500					✓
101356		8600	6° F	350			✓		
101423			6° F			In Cu 2	✓	✓	✓
101700		5000	6° F			Out of (below) Cu 2			
102317		100	6° F			Interrupt profile descent			
	P1	→ 50	6° F			Re start descent			
102608	R1.1	100	6° F			Start of run			
102715		100	6° F	750			✓		
102338	R1.1	100	174 A						
102950	R1.1	100	174 A	1000			✓		
103108	R1.1	100	174 A			END OF Run			
	R1.2	100	174 A			START OF Run			
103335	P2					START OF PROFILE CLIMB			
		3000				END OF PROFILE CLIMB			
104036	R2.1	3000	174 A			Start of run			
104125	R2.1	3000	174 A			Entered cloud (Cu 2)			
105825	R2.1?	3000	174 A			Entering cloud			
100814			6° F			Head to Zenith			
100924	P3	300	174° A			Head to Nadir			
110940	P3					Start of profile 3			
111051	P3	4300	174° A	750		Trist Time check	✓		
			174° A	300					✓
			174° A	500					✓
111116	P3	4300	174° A			End of profile 3			
111346	R3.1	4300	174° A			Start of run			
						Cu 2 clearing			
114400	R4.1	100	174° A			END OF Run			
114400	R4.1	100	174° A			START OF Run			
115958	R4.1	100	174° A			END OF Run			
120603	P4	100	174° A			Profile climb			
125436	R5.1	100	06° F			START OF Run			
124859	R5.1	100	06° F	250		Dark		✓	
124918	R5.1	100	06° F			SCENE ALL			
125119	P6	100	06° F			End of run start of profile			
125743	P6	8300	06° F	500			✓		
125840	P6	8500	06° F			End of profile climb			
130001	R6.1	8500	06° F			Start of run			
130101	R6.1	8500	06° F	250		Scene on USM			✓
130532	R6.1	8500	06° F			End of run			
131508	R7.1					Start of run (Through Cu 2)			
133307	P7	13000	06° F			End of profile			
133807	R8.1	13000				Start of run			

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	23/01/07	Flight	B261	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on			at time	0840		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	275	Cold	275		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	0845ish		
Scan indication		Monitor	•		Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual	
Weather Blocking H w/ Nerly. Sshine & showers	Cloud	Patchy Ci	Precip	N/a		
	Surface	dry	Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	09:26:13		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	338	Cold	275	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
		34.2	37.5	39.2	42.1	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again				at time		

Flight:

B261

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:

- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 05/02/2007 11:35:49

Last Updated:

23/01/2007 16:18:47

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B261

Date: 22th January 2007

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TW not fitted
3. Heimann – no in-flight calibrations
4. Turbulence probe. P0 froze several times at relatively low-level. Unfrozen by low-level runs (temp +3 degC). All inlets froze in later high-level flying.
5. Nevzorov total water failed.
6. Data not recording to disk pre-flight. Unable to unload disk except by rebooting HORACE.
7. FM PC crashed in flight
8. DEIMOS not turned off correctly & not operated on this flight. Resultant noise on some instruments.
9. PCASP, FFSSP, 2DP all have some noisy data (see point 8)

Aircraft

Interference on intercom

Satcom H Calls

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: ~~21~~ 23/1/07

Flight No: 3261

Pre-Flighter: PALS

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	NO CO
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	SIPA A - not loaded
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Done checked
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	no filled
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	not filled
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	not finding temp PS / target.
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	not filled
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	not used.
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	<i>not fitted</i>
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX	applied	
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps	empty (weekly only)	

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B261:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x For/Rearward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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